

NONLINEAR SNAPPING CHARACTERISTICS FOR LAMINATED CYLINDRICAL PANELS WITH HIGH-ORDER SHEAR DEFORMATION THEORY

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ABSTRACT

The snapping analysis including a higher order displacement expression, in conjunction with nonlinear deformation shell theory for the investigation of laminated composite cylindrical shells under large deformation, is examined. The second Piola stress and Green strain tensors are incorporated in this research. Furthermore, both static and dynamic features of a cylindrical panel during the snapping process are discussed.

1. INTRODUCTION

In certain geometric configurations of shell structures instability is displayed by a very quick reversal of the displacement field. This phenomenon is defined as snapping. It characterizes the passing of an unstable state of equilibrium to one of stability. In many cases, one can observe the physical features occurring in the structures movement by following a load verse displacement curve for a discretely located point. This instability phenomenon can only be examined when the nonlinear displacement terms are included in the kinematic relations. Depending on a specific situation, some of the nonlinear displacement terms may be considered negligible to simplify the problem. For instance, many of rotational terms are discarded in the Donnell type shell equations. This formulation, as a result, can only accurately predict moderate rotation problems. A similar situation is also shown in the Von Karman plate equations where many nonlinear rotational terms have been ignored for the large deflection analysis of plates owing to bending. A sound review in the area of geometrical nonlinear composite plates was given by Chia[1]. By the same token, partial nonlinear strain-displacement relations were mentioned in that review. For a deep shell panel undergoing snapping, the local rotations may become large which is beyond the accuracy of the previously mentioned theory. Thus, the use of full nonlinear displacement terms in the kinematic relations becomes necessary to properly describe the responses of large displacements and large rotations for a cylindrical shell during the snapping process. Dennis and Palazotto[2] employed the full second-order nonlinear displacement terms based on a total Lagrangian coordinate approach assuming Green elastic strain kinematic relations for the nonlinear static analysis of laminated

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composite cylindrical shells. Yet, only linear displacement term are considered in the transverse shear strains and the normal transverse strain is neglected. A 36 degree of freedom isoparametric quadrilateral shell element, which consists of seven degrees of freedom at each corner node and two in-plane displacement degrees of freedom at the center node on each side, including bending rotations and shear deformation, was developed as shown in Figure 1. In the present research, this 36 degree of freedom shell element is incorporated to investigate the static and dynamic responses of a laminated cylindrical panel when snapping occurs.

Laminated composite shells have the requirement that the transverse shears must be considered, which the traditional Kirchhoff-Love hypotheses are inadequate to describe. Due to the potential large directional variations of stiffness properties in laminated composite structures, the three dimensional effects may become very significant. In other words, the transverse shears can not be neglected for the appropriate analysis of laminated composite structures. Various theories of transverse shear effects on laminated composite plates were discussed by Reddy[3]. As indicated in [3], the layer-wise third-order shear deformation theory, which accounts for parabolic distribution of the transverse shears and requires no shear correction coefficients, seems to be adequate in representing the global response of laminated plates. Different approaches for developing two-dimensional shear deformation theories for multilayered composite plates and shells were reviewed by Noor and Burton[4,5]. Extensive numerical results showing the effects of the variation in various two-dimensional shear deformation theories were presented in those reviews. The plausible higher order two-dimensional shell displacement functions, which lead to the second-order transverse shear strains are employed in the present study. These second-order transverse shear strains, due to the linear displacement-strain relation in the transverse or thickness direction, are distributed parabolically through the thickness coordinate of a shell and vanish on both top and bottom surfaces.

The Riks[6] nonlinear solution technique is invoked for the load-deflection curve in the static analysis. Algorithms based on the Newton-Raphson iterative method and the beta-m[7] method, which is a generalization of Newmark time marching integration scheme, are incorporated in the dynamics solution.

2. FORMULATIONS

2.1 Kinematics

The displacement-strain relations including all the in-plane non-linear terms, and accounting for the transverse shear effects for large displacement and rotation analyses of a cylindrical shell are shown in [2]. For convenience, a brief review of this theory may be helpful. The approach of a shell problem based on assuming displacements as power series in the thickness coordinate ξ is apparently attributed to Basset[8]. It follows that the three-dimensional behavior of a shell can be fully described by the two-dimensional behavior, which is a function only of the middle surface coordinate ξ_1 and ξ_2 , of the shell. Accordingly, the higher order two-dimensional shell displacement functions used in the present study for an arbitrary shell described by orthogonal curvilinear coordinates are written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 u_1(\xi_1, \xi_2, \xi) &= u\left(1 - \frac{\xi}{R_1}\right) + \xi\psi_1 + \xi^2\phi_1 + \xi^3\gamma_1 + \xi^4\theta_1 \\
 u_2(\xi_1, \xi_2, \xi) &= v\left(1 - \frac{\xi}{R_2}\right) + \xi\psi_2 + \xi^2\phi_2 + \xi^3\gamma_2 + \xi^4\theta_2 \\
 u_3(\xi_1, \xi_2) &= w
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

where u , v , and w are the displacements of a point on the middle surface, ψ_1 and ψ_2 are rotations of the normals at $\xi = 0$ to the midsurface with respect to ξ_2 axis and ξ_1 axis, respectively, R_1 and R_2 are radii of curvature along ξ_1 and ξ_2 directions, respectively, and ϕ_α , γ_α , and θ_α , ($\alpha = 1,2$) are functions to be determined. All of u , v , w , ψ_α , ϕ_α , γ_α , and θ_α , ($\alpha = 1,2$) are functions of ξ_1 and ξ_2 only. The assumed displacements in eq.(1) is dictated by the desire to present the second-order parabolically distributed shear strains through the thickness coordinate and by the requirement that the transverse normal strain, $\epsilon_{33} = \epsilon_3$, be zero.

If one keeps only the linear displacement terms in the transverse shear strains in the orthogonal curvilinear coordinate, the following is obtained.

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_{23} &= \epsilon_4 = \frac{1}{h_2}(u_{3,2} + h_2 u_{2,3} - u_2 h_{2,3}) \\ \epsilon_{13} &= \epsilon_5 = \frac{1}{h_1}(u_{3,1} + h_1 u_{1,3} - u_1 h_{1,3})\end{aligned}\quad (2)$$

where $h_1 = \alpha_1(1 - \xi/R_1)$, $h_2 = \alpha_2(1 - \xi/R_2)$, $h_3 = 1$, and α_1^2 and α_2^2 are the surface metric coefficients. The $(\)_{,\alpha}$ ($\alpha = 1,2$) refers to differentiation with respect to ξ_α and $(\)_{,3}$ refers to differentiation with respect to ξ .

Now, eq.(1) is substituted into eq.(2) and the vanish conditions of the transverse shear strains on the top and the bottom surfaces of a shell are applied, i.e.

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_4(\xi_1, \xi_2, \pm \frac{h}{2}) &= 0 \\ \epsilon_5(\xi_1, \xi_2, \pm \frac{h}{2}) &= 0\end{aligned}\quad (3)$$

the following are obtained.

$$\begin{aligned}\phi_1 &= \phi_2 = 0 \\ \theta_1 &= \frac{\gamma_1}{2 R_1} \\ \theta_2 &= \frac{\gamma_2}{2 R_2} \\ (1 - \frac{h^2}{8 R_1^2})\gamma_1 &\approx \gamma_1 = \frac{-4}{3 h^2}(\psi_1 + \frac{w_{,1}}{\alpha_1}) \\ (1 - \frac{h^2}{8 R_2^2})\gamma_2 &\approx \gamma_2 = \frac{-4}{3 h^2}(\psi_2 + \frac{w_{,2}}{\alpha_2})\end{aligned}\quad (4)$$

where h is the thickness of the shell. The γ_1 and γ_2 in eq(4) are simplified by discarding the high order terms. As can be seen, these higher order terms are negligible compared to unity even for a fairly thick shell. Moreover, the θ_1 and θ_2 in eq.(4) can also be ignored due to their higher order natures.

Substituting eq.(4) into eq.(1), the general shell displacement functions are obtained

$$\begin{aligned}u_1(\xi_1, \xi_2, \xi) &= u(1 - \frac{\xi}{R_1}) + \xi\psi_1 + \xi^3 k(\psi_1 + \frac{w_{,1}}{\alpha_1}) \\ u_2(\xi_1, \xi_2, \xi) &= v(1 - \frac{\xi}{R_2}) + \xi\psi_2 + \xi^3 k(\psi_2 + \frac{w_{,2}}{\alpha_2}) \\ u_3(\xi_1, \xi_2) &= w\end{aligned}\quad (5)$$

where $k = -4/3 h^2$. The cubic term coefficient $-\beta_1 = \psi_1 + w_{,1}/\alpha_1$ in u_1 shown in eq.(5) represents the shear rotation which combines with the rotation of the normal ψ_1 due to bending to give the total rotation of the elastic curve $w_{,1}$. A similar situation for $-\beta_2 = \psi_2 + w_{,2}/\alpha_2$ is also given in u_2 .

The kinematic of a shell with the capabilities of undergoing large displacements/large rotations and transverse shear deformation for the study of snapping characteristics can now be derived by means of eq.(5). The eq.(5) gives two-dimensional higher order displacement functions which, in conjunction with eq.(2), represents parabolically distributed shear effects through the thickness direction and satisfies the zero shear boundary conditions on both top and bottom surfaces of a shell. It follows that the transverse shear strains ϵ_4 and ϵ_5 are then obtained by substituting eq.(5) into eq.(2) and by neglecting the higher order terms.

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_4 &= \frac{1}{h_2}(w_{,2} + \alpha_2\psi_2)\left(1 - \frac{4\xi^2}{h^2}\right) \\ \epsilon_5 &= \frac{1}{h_1}(w_{,1} + \alpha_1\psi_1)\left(1 - \frac{4\xi^2}{h^2}\right)\end{aligned}\quad (6)$$

Furthermore, the full in-plane displacement-strain relations including all the nonlinear displacement terms in the orthogonal curvilinear coordinate are

$$\begin{aligned}\epsilon_1 &= \frac{1}{h_1^2}\left\{h_1\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial \xi_1} + \frac{h_1 u_2}{h_2}\frac{\partial h_1}{\partial \xi_2} + \frac{h_1 u_3}{h_3}\frac{\partial h_1}{\partial \xi} + \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial \xi_1} + \frac{u_2}{h_2}\frac{\partial h_1}{\partial \xi_2} + \frac{u_3}{h_3}\frac{\partial h_1}{\partial \xi}\right)^2\right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{\partial u_2}{\partial \xi_1} - \frac{u_1}{h_2}\frac{\partial h_1}{\partial \xi_2}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{\partial u_3}{\partial \xi_1} - \frac{u_1}{h_3}\frac{\partial h_1}{\partial \xi}\right)^2\right\} \\ \epsilon_2 &= \frac{1}{h_2^2}\left\{h_2\frac{\partial u_2}{\partial \xi_2} + \frac{h_2 u_3}{h_3}\frac{\partial h_2}{\partial \xi} + \frac{h_2 u_1}{h_1}\frac{\partial h_2}{\partial \xi_1} + \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{\partial u_2}{\partial \xi_2} + \frac{u_3}{h_3}\frac{\partial h_2}{\partial \xi} + \frac{u_1}{h_1}\frac{\partial h_2}{\partial \xi_1}\right)^2\right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{\partial u_3}{\partial \xi_2} - \frac{u_2}{h_3}\frac{\partial h_2}{\partial \xi}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial \xi_2} - \frac{u_2}{h_1}\frac{\partial h_2}{\partial \xi_1}\right)^2\right\} \\ \epsilon_6 &= \frac{2}{h_1 h_2}\left\{\frac{1}{2}\left(h_1\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial \xi_2} + h_2\frac{\partial u_2}{\partial \xi_1} - u_2\frac{\partial h_2}{\partial \xi_1} - u_1\frac{\partial h_1}{\partial \xi_2}\right)\right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial \xi_2} - \frac{u_2}{h_1}\frac{\partial h_2}{\partial \xi_1}\right)\left(\frac{\partial u_1}{\partial \xi_1} + \frac{u_2}{h_2}\frac{\partial h_1}{\partial \xi_2} + \frac{u_3}{h_3}\frac{\partial h_1}{\partial \xi}\right)\right. \\ &\quad \left. + \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{\partial u_2}{\partial \xi_1} - \frac{u_1}{h_2}\frac{\partial h_1}{\partial \xi_2}\right)\left(\frac{\partial u_2}{\partial \xi_2} + \frac{u_1}{h_1}\frac{\partial h_2}{\partial \xi_1} + \frac{u_3}{h_3}\frac{\partial h_2}{\partial \xi}\right) + \frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{\partial u_3}{\partial \xi_1} - \frac{u_1}{h_3}\frac{\partial h_1}{\partial \xi}\right)\left(\frac{\partial u_3}{\partial \xi_2} - \frac{u_2}{h_3}\frac{\partial h_2}{\partial \xi}\right)\right\}\end{aligned}\quad (7)$$

Substituting eq.(5) into eq.(7), the in-plane strains with full nonlinear displacement terms are thus obtained. The stresses in a laminated composite shell can then be derived by incorporating the laminated constitutive theory with eqs.(6) and (7) in a straightforward manner.

Finally, for a cylindrical panel with radius R , the eqs.(6) and (7) can be further simplified by letting $\alpha_1 = 1$, $R_1 = \infty$, and $\alpha_2 = R_2 = R$.

The investigation has been separated into two areas of research. First, the static snap through of a cylindrical panel under a transversely concentrated load and second; the phenomenon of dynamic shell response related to the shell snapping.

2.2 Static Analysis

In the study of instability characteristics of shells, a limit point on the nonlinear load-displacement curve separates the stable and unstable regions. At this limit point the stiffness matrix becomes singular and an iteration method does not

converge. Consequently, the solution may jump to the next stable region and lose the trace of the load-displacement curve in the unstable region. Many solution techniques for solving nonlinear problems with limit points have been developed. The most commonly used solution techniques can be classified as: the displacement control method, the load control method and the arc length (Riks[6]) method. Each of these methods differs in the use of the incremental scheme and the constraint conditions. The arc length solution method not only predict the snap through phenomenon, but can also trace the snap back occurrence. Thus, among these methods, the most satisfactory one, and used in the present research, for solving geometrically nonlinear static problems is the arc length method combining with the Newton-Raphson iteration scheme within each incremental step. This solution technique is outlined in the following and the detail algorithms should be addressed in [9].

The finite element equation of a geometrically nonlinear cylindrical panel is derived as

$$[\mathbf{K}]\{u\} = \{F\} \quad (8)$$

where $\{u\}$ is the displacement vector, $\{F\}$ is the applied force, and $[\mathbf{K}]$ is the nonlinear stiffness matrix which can be written as

$$[\mathbf{K}] = [K + \frac{N_1}{2} + \frac{N_2}{3}] \quad (9)$$

where $[K]$ is a constant stiffness matrix, $[N_1]$ is a linear stiffness matrix, and $[N_2]$ is a quadratic stiffness matrix. For the purpose of employing the Riks nonlinear solution technique, a scalar loading parameter λ is introduced in eq.(8), which yields

$$G(\{u\}, \lambda) = [\mathbf{K}]\{u\} - \lambda\{F\} = 0 \quad (10)$$

Note that a constraint condition is required in the Riks solution technique to direct the path of convergence. A usual constraint condition is established by introducing a fixed 'arc length' Δl to a prescribed value such that

$$\{\Delta u_n\}^T \{\Delta u_n\} + \Delta \lambda_n^2 \{F\}^T \{F\} = \Delta l^2 \quad (11)$$

where $\{\Delta u_n\}$, $\Delta \lambda_n$ are the values for each incremental step, and n is the incremental number.

The Newton-Raphson iteration scheme is then applied at each incremental step, which results in a system of equations of $\{\delta u_i\}$

$$[\mathbf{K}_T]\{\delta u_i\} = \delta \lambda_i \{F\} - G(\{u_i\}, \lambda_i) \quad (12)$$

where $[\mathbf{K}_T]$ is the updated tangential stiffness matrix and is written as

$$[\mathbf{K}_T] = [K + N_1 + N_2] \quad (13)$$

$\{\delta u_i\}$, $\delta \lambda_i$ are the updated values in each iteration and i is the iteration number. Combing eq.(12) and eq.(11) gives a system of $N+1$ equations with $N+1$ unknowns, $\{\delta u_i\}$ and $\delta \lambda_i$.

2.3 Dynamic Analysis

The beta-m[7] method, which is a generalization of Newmark time marching integration scheme, along with the Newton-Raphson iterative technique are used in the present study for the dynamics analysis. This method provides a general single step algorithm applicable to initial value problems and is specialized by

specifying the method order m along with m integration parameters, $\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2, \dots, \beta_{m-1}$. For a particular choice of m , the integration parameters provide a subfamily of methods which control accuracy and stability. The beta- m method is defined as

$$u_{n+1}^{(k)} = q_k + b_k \Delta u^{(m)} \quad (14)$$

where

$$q_k = \sum_{j=k}^m \frac{u_n^{(j)} h^{j-k}}{(j-k)!} \quad (15)$$

and

$$b_k = \frac{\beta_k h^{m-k}}{(m-k)!} \quad (16)$$

and $k = 0, 1, 2, \dots, m$. The β_m in eq.(10) is defined to equal one and h is the time increment for each time step. The method order m implies that $u_n^{(m)}$ is the highest derivative to be retained. In the present study, m equals 2 which happens to be the case of Newmark time integration scheme. Additionally, $\beta_0 = 0.5, \beta_1 = 0.5$, and $\beta_2 = 1.0$, are suggested[7] for an unconditionally stable analysis.

The dynamic equation of a geometrically nonlinear cylindrical panel is written as

$$[\mathbf{M}]\{\ddot{u}\} + [\mathbf{K}]\{u\} = \{F(t)\} \quad (17)$$

where $\{\ddot{u}\}$ is the acceleration vector, $\{F(t)\}$ is the time dependent applied force, $[\mathbf{M}]$ is the consistent mass matrix, and $[\mathbf{K}]$ is shown in eq.(9).

By substituting eq.(14) into eq.(17) at time t_{n+1} . One obtains

$$\begin{aligned} & [b_2 \mathbf{M} + b_0 \mathbf{K}(q_0 + \Delta u^{(m)})] \Delta u^{(m)} = \\ & P_{n+1} - \{\mathbf{M}q_2 + \mathbf{K}(q_0 + b_0 \Delta u^{(m)})q_0\} \end{aligned} \quad (18)$$

where P_{n+1} is the applied load at time t_{n+1} , b_0, b_1, b_2 are scalars dependent on the integration parameters as shown in eq.(16), and q_0, q_1, q_2 are history vectors known at time t_n as shown in eq.(15). Eq. (18) results in a set of nonlinear algebraic equations. Thus, the Newton-Raphson iterative method is incorporated herein to solve eq.(18). At each time step, the following assumption is made

$$\Delta u_{i+1}^{(m)} = \Delta u_i^{(m)} + \delta u_i^{(m)} \quad (19)$$

where i is the iteration number. Applying the Newton-Raphson method to eq.(18) and using eq.(19) one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} & [b_2 \mathbf{M} + b_0 \mathbf{K}_T(q_0 + b_0 \Delta u_i^{(m)})] \delta u_i^{(m)} = \\ & P_{n+1} - \mathbf{M}\{q_2 + b_2 \Delta u_i^{(m)}\} \\ & - \mathbf{K}(q_0 + b_0 \Delta u_i^{(m)})\{q_0 + b_0 \Delta u_i^{(m)}\} \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

where $[\mathbf{K}_T]$ is the updated tangential stiffness matrix and is defined in eq.(13).

As a result, eq.(20) gives the basic algorithm for the dynamic analysis in the present research. Some dynamic results regarding the nonlinear snapping characteristics of composite cylindrical panels are discussed by the authors [10].

3. EXAMPLES

An eight ply $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$ laminated cylindrical panel with a radius of curvature $R = 12$ inches, an open angle $\theta = 1.0$ radian, and length $L = 11$ inches is first analyzed due to a concentrated load P applied transversely at the center of the panel. The cylindrical panel has two clamped boundaries along straight sides and two free circular boundaries. Each ply is made from the AS4-350 graphite epoxy material and has the thickness $h = 0.005$ inches. The material properties of the AS4-350 graphite epoxy are summarized as the follows: $E_{11} = 20.46E6$ psi, $E_{22} = 1.34E6$ psi, $G_{12} = G_{13} = 0.8638E6$ psi, $G_{23} = 0.43E6$ psi, and $\nu_{12} = 0.313$.

The Riks nonlinear solution technique, i.e. the arc length method, is employed for the nonlinear analysis. The displacement versus load curve at the load applied point is displayed in Figure 2. Different values of the load parameter and convergence criteria which are required in the Riks technique are utilized in this study. Nevertheless, the values of the critical load obtained in those cases are almost indistinguishable. Moreover, for the nature of $[\pm 45]$ plies, the nonlinear effects can introduce errors in the use of a quarter panel model [11]. To avoid the situation, the full cylindrical panel is modeled by 16×24 equal size elements for the snapping analysis.

The second example in the present research considers a 24 plies $[0_6/90_6]_s$ simply supported AS4-3501-6 graphite epoxy laminated composite cylindrical panel subjected to a transverse center concentrated load. Again a radius of curvature $R = 12$ inches is used along with an open angle $\theta = 1.0$ radian. The sizes of 49 elements varying from 2 in. \times 1 in. to 0.5 in. \times 0.5 in. are employed for the analysis of a quarter of the panel due to symmetry. A length of 18 inches is used herein. The static analysis of this problem has been studied [12] and shows the critical snapping load to be approximately 2800 lb.

A step load, with the load amplitude of 2000 lb. which is lower than the critical snapping load, is applied in the dynamic analysis. The loading history and the response versus time are shown in Figure 3. As can be seen, the response oscillates periodically and reaches the steady state condition. Moreover, the periodic response oscillating about the equilibrium position represents the static solution. However, as the applied load reaches the critical snapping load, the solution become erratic. Figure 4. presents the loading history and the dynamic response for two different time steps when the load capacity of applied step load becomes 3000 lb. which is only slightly beyond the critical snapping load. The smaller time step of 0.0001 second obviously gives a better result than the large time step of 0.0002 second. A reasonable periodic feature is observed for only one and half cycles for the time step 0.0001 second and then the solution starts to behave in a fashion which can be classified as a non-steady state solution. It is believed that the large number of calculations performed, the nonlinearity of the strain-displacement equations, the precision in the computer code and the round-off of the computer may be reasons for variations in the solution. Yet, it is also possible that the function being studied, a discrete point oscillation, is no longer valid for expressing the panels nonlinear movement.

4. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

The kinematics including the full second-order in-plane nonlinear displacement terms and linear transverse displacement terms are employed in this research for the nonlinear analysis of laminated composite shells undergoing large displacements and large rotations when snapping occurs. Since only linear transverse shear strains are discussed, the allowable rotations are somewhat limited. Additionally, the compatibility conditions involve

the transverse shear strains can not be satisfied. However, for the situations where some of the rotational terms are small (40° or less [2]), these compatibility equations are better approximated.

The plausible fourth order two-dimensional shell displacement functions are introduced, which, in conjunction with the zero shear boundary conditions at the top and bottom surfaces of the shell, result in the second-order transverse shear strains that distributed parabolically through the thickness coordinate. These second-order transverse shear functions, which avoid the shear locking and shear correction coefficient problems, give a transverse shear effect that can not always be neglected especially in laminated composite shells.

The Riks nonlinear solution technique for static analysis, and the beta-m numerical algorithms for dynamic analysis, are also reviewed. Two illustrated problems are incorporated to show the nonlinear snapping characteristics of laminated cylindrical panels.

Due to the potential errors which result from using the symmetry in-plane conditions on a $[\pm 45]$ stacking sequence, a full panel model was analyzed. The effectness of applying symmetry condition on $[\pm 45]$ stacking sequence is further studied by the authors. A step load is used to investigate the dynamic response of laminated composite panel during the snapping process. The steady state condition as well as the periodic fashion oscillating about the equilibrium position are observed as the load amplitude is lower than the critical snapping load. The situation, where the load amplitude is slightly beyond the critical snapping load, is particularly discussed.

5. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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Figure 1. 36 degree of freedom isoparametric quadrilateral shell element with seven degrees of freedom at each corner node and two inplane displacement degrees of freedom at the center node on each side.

Figure 2. Displacement versus load curve at the load applied point for the eight ply $[0/\pm 45/90]_s$ laminated cylindrical panel with a concentrated load P applied transversely at the center of the panel.

Figure 3. Loading history and dynamic response for the center of the laminated composite cylindrical panel when the applied load is lower than the critical snapping load.

Figure 4. Loading history and dynamic response for the center of the laminated composite cylindrical panel when the applied load is slightly beyond the critical snapping load with two different time steps, 0.0001 seconds and 0.0002 seconds.